

PSYCHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS IN SCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN

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Mahmudjonov Ibrohimjon

Andijan State University, Faculty of Socio-Economics

2nd year student of pedagogy and psychology

Abstract: *This article analyzes the role and importance of psychological conditions of school age, school actions, and methods for pedagogues. It is important to determine the temping of the school age, and to work accordingly.*

Keywords: *Individual words: individual words, education, corruption, reader, ability, child, behavior, immovection, pedagogue.*

It is no exaggeration to say that today in the world the focus is on the education of children, the role of psychologists is very important in the proper organization of the upbringing of children. Not to mention the role of school psychologists. School psychology is a field that applies the following principles.

School psychology, educational psychology, developmental psychology, clinical psychology. It also works with students and parents to meet the mental and physical health needs of children and adolescents. Mankind has emerged, the concept of education, how to implement it, what is important in education, why is education important? What aspects should be focused on? Everyone approaches from the point of view of their worldview, and each nation approaches from the point of view of its own mentality. learns and resolves positively. Well-known pediatrician for children "Benjamin Spock" writes: "After 6 years, the child loves his parents deeply, but does not try to show it. He at least does not like to kiss in front of other people. The child treats other people coldly, only those who think they are 'wonderful people'. he doesn't want to be loved like a child. He respects himself and wants to be respected. To get rid of his parental addiction, he becomes an adult who believes in ideas and knowledge outside of his family... What his parents taught him will not be forgotten, and their principles of good and evil are deeply rooted in his heart. He considers their opinions. But when he is reminded of what his parents need to do, he gets angry because he knows it and wants to be conscious. "

Development of mental processes: The child's vocabulary increased to 7,000 words. It is very important for speech development. The urgent need to develop balanced speech, which is the basis for language improvement during this period, is to analyze the voice of child masters. The child learns the basics of contextual speech, which is an indicator of his development.

Thinking. Thinking is the most important task in young students. The formation of logical thinking is a sign of proper mental development of children at this age. At school, the teacher must first analyze the mental state of students, it is recommended to use teaching methods, taking into account the innate characteristics of the nervous system (temperament). , it is advisable to use methods.

As mentioned above, human temperaments:

Choleric temperament is curious, aggressive, easy to react to events, and quick to get angry. Experiences vary with activity. He devotes himself to the work with all his being, feels his strength and tries to overcome the difficulties encountered on the way to achieve the goal. When he runs out of energy, he gets into trouble and has no choice but to work. The will of the choleric is very strong.

Sanguine temperament is a very calm type, the nervous process is active and well balanced. He is a very good, healthy, cheerful member of the society, but these abilities will be visible only when he finds a job that interests him. Sanguine calm, quickly adapts to the situation, quickly communicates with people around him, does not feel uncomfortable in the company of strangers. He is cheerful, cheerful, quick-witted and always busy with something. It changes its character quickly due to the mobility of nervous processes. Suffers in bad situations. He is generally optimistic.

Phlegmatic temperament is characterized by a relative suppression of the relative mobility of the nerve, the processes of excitation and inhibition. These are calm, resilient and very hardworking people. They do not lose their composure, even in the most difficult situations. Due to the severity of the nervous process, they behave well and do not get excited immediately. They don't want to be distracted by small things, so they move in a constant and methodical tension that requires the same amount of effort. IP Pavlov rated the endurance of this type of people as very high.

Melancholy temperament is characterized by a weak ability to work, that is, their level of excitement and inhibition is very weak. They are intimidated by the news, the new conditions, the way they interact with

people, so they become human. They do not exclude their inner world and find it difficult to adapt to living conditions.

In short, the young school age is a classic period in the formation of moral ideas and rules. Of course, a child's significant contribution to the moral world leads to early childhood, but the principle of "rules" and "laws", the concept of "norm", "obligation" - all these are specific features of moral psychology, which is determined and formed at the age of school age . Proper upbringing of a child from an early age is of course important not to have a strong impact on his psychology.

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